

ANAEMIA AMONG WORKING WOMEN WITH DIFFERENT JOB RANKINGS; PREVALENCE, LIFESTYLE MODIFICATION, TREATMENT AND FOLLOW-UP

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: IDA majorly depresses everyday activities. IDA among working women in India remains underexplored.

Methodology: A prospective interventional study was performed in working women with 4 different job rankings (teaching staff to gardeners and peons). After ethical clearance, detailed history for symptoms and signs, haemoglobin was estimated using cyanmethhaemoglobin method to classify as normal, mild, moderate and severely anaemic. Active management was done by lifestyle-modifications, deworming with Tab. Albendazole and oral iron-therapy based on WHO guidelines. Haemoglobin was re-estimated after 1 month of treatment.

Results: Moderate degree of anaemia was seen in all categories of working women with no correlation to symptoms. Only category D patients (housekeeping/security/gardening) showed correlation but could not initiate therapy due to financial crises. 50% of subject in all categories followed suggested life style changes and take medications. This was mainly due to lack of time management. Reporting for follow-up Hb was 33% except Category A (Teaching faculty-47% reported). This was mainly due to fear of figure prick.

Conclusion: Working women multi-task ignoring their own health. Assessment of anaemia among these women can show the cause of lack of enthusiasm and concentration for everyday routine. Also approach to treatment should be directed towards the reasons of non-compliance.

Key words: Anaemia; working women; prevalence; follow-up; cyanmethemoglobin method

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) definition of anaemia as haemoglobin (Hb) concentration <130 g/L in men, and <120 g/L in women.¹ In low- and middle-income countries, about 1.2 billion people are infected with roundworm and more than 700 million are infected with hookworm or whipworm. ² Presence of chronic infection interferes with erythropoiesis. Iron deficiency may impair cellular responses and immune functions and consequently increase the susceptibility to infections. Moreover, the recovery from infections may be prolonged. Anaemia adversely affects physical work capacity and cognition. Anaemia, even when mild, causes a significant impairment of maximal work capacity thereby productivity which adversely affect the economy.³

India has very high prevalence of anaemia. Nutritional anaemia is a major public health problem and is primarily due to iron deficiency. Percentage prevalence of anaemia among adolescent girls in the age group 15–19 years and in the older age group 20–29 years remains almost stagnant at 55.8 per cent and 56.1 per cent respectively.⁴

Common causes of Nutritional Anaemia of women are insufficient quantity of iron-rich foods and “iron enhancers” in the diet, excessive quantity of “iron inhibitors” in diet especially during mealtimes (e.g., tea, coffee; calcium-rich foods), iron loss during menstruation, poor iron stores from infancy, childhood deficiencies and adolescent anaemia, iron loss from post-partum haemorrhage, increased iron requirement due to tissue, blood and energy requirements during pregnancy, teenage pregnancy, repeated pregnancies with less than 2 years’ interval, iron loss due to parasite load (e.g., malaria, intestinal worms), poor environmental sanitation and unsafe drinking water.⁴ Based on guidelines put up by WHO and by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare Govt. of India, treatment for nutritional deficiency anaemia (iron and folic acid deficiency) is deworming using Tab. Albendazole 400mg biannually followed by 100 mg elemental iron and 500 mcg of folic acid in women of reproductive age groups.^{1,4} The amount of elemental iron and folic acid used varies in different grades of anaemia.⁵⁻⁷

There is clear evidence to support prompt treatment in all patients with iron deficiency anaemia because it is known that treatment improves quality of life and physical condition as well as alleviates fatigue and cognitive deficits. Although clear evidence is lacking, iron deficiency without anaemia is associated with RLS and chronic fatigue, and treatment alleviates these symptoms. In CHF, iron replacement therapy has been shown to be beneficial, even when anaemia is not present. Thus, the decision to treat iron deficiency in a patient without manifest anaemia is crucial. Oral iron is readily available, inexpensive, and convenient, making it a viable treatment option. The main disadvantage of intravenous iron is the necessity for administration by a health care professional, with the associated costs. Blood transfusion should be highly restricted in chronic iron deficiency anaemia, patients with active bleeding who are hemodynamically unstable, with critical anaemia (Hb level <7 g/dL), acute myocardial ischemia, or if all other treatments fail.⁸⁻¹¹

The response to therapy should be carefully monitored. The Hb level should increase by 2 g/dL within 4 to 8 weeks, although some patients may report an improved sense of well-being after a few days. If the Hb level does not respond appropriately within this time frame, treatment should be modified (changed to intravenous iron) and the cause of the lack of response evaluated. Depending on the severity of the deficiency and underlying cause, normalization of the Hb level may take up to 3 months, and it may take longer to replace iron stores (ferritin >100 µg/L).⁸⁻¹²

The effectiveness of a treatment depends on both the efficacy of a medication and patient compliance to the therapeutic regimen. Previous studies have indicated lesser prevalence of nutritional deficiency anaemia among working women, but the Indian scenario remains yet to be disclosed.¹³ Also variations and measures of compliance related to job ranking remain obscure.

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess prevalence and grades of anaemia among working women of different job rankings.
2. Advising lifestyle modifications and giving active treatment to anaemic working women.
3. Follow up of anaemic working women after 4 weeks of lifestyle modification and treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

After approval from institutional ethical committee and registration in clinical trial registry- India, this study was conducted in the department during college hours. Women who are pregnant, lactating, of extreme age group, history of hypertension, diabetes, any other hormonal imbalance, any medical or surgical illness, familial or genetic disorders were excluded from the study. Also subjects receiving treatment under “IFA treatment programme” were excluded from the study.² Women were categorised into 4 groups based on employment status mentioned under the college regulations.

- **Category A:** Teaching faculty (Tutors/Jr resident/Sr. resident/Assistant professor/Associate professor/Professors/Head of Dept) and senior managers.
- **Category B:** staff nurse/Managers/assistant managers/Supervisors.
- **Category C:** senior office assistant/office assistant/lab. Technician/paramedical MSWs.
- **Category D:** housekeeping/security/gardening.

Study Protocol

In the age group of 21 to 50 years, minimum of 30 subjects were taken in each category. After well explained written and informed consent, an elaborate past history, family history, menstrual history, number of years of employment and job

ranking were acquired. Signs and symptoms related to nutritional deficiency anaemia like lethargy, giddiness, postural changes, pallor, koilonychias, tachycardia, murmurs was assessed.^{1, 14}

Based on signs and symptoms (S/S), subjects were categorised into 2 groups; less than 2 S/S and ≥ 2 S/S.

Assessment and grading of anaemia: After taking all aseptic precautions, capillary blood was collected using a pricking device and haemoglobin was estimated using “Cyanmethemoglobin method”.¹⁰ Based on WHO guidelines, grading of anaemia for non-pregnant women was taken as normal $>12\text{gm}\%$; mild = $11 - 11.9\text{gm}\%$; moderate = $8 - 10.9\text{gm}\%$; severe $< 8\text{gm}\%$.¹⁵

Treatment protocol: treatment was given free of cost. based on reports from WHO and Ministry of Health and Family welfare.^{4, 6, 15}

- ❖ Lifestyle modification: Dietary diversification was encouraged. Diet chart was given to all participants with do's and don'ts in diet in local language. Consumption of micronutrient rich foods – e.g. green leafy vegetables, whole pulses, jaggery, meat, poultry and fish, fruits and black gram, groundnuts, ragi, whole grains, milk, eggs, meat and nuts, lentils and vitamin C rich fruits – which may be available but are underutilised by the deficient population was encouraged.
- ❖ **Deworming:** Tab. Albendazole 400mg single dose in all women who haven't had deworming in last 6 months was given.
- ❖ **Iron and folic acid therapy:** A common generic approach for iron deficiency in adults consists of a daily dose of 150-200 mg of elemental iron. Assuming that 10% of the iron is absorbed, the hemoglobin concentration may fully correct after 4 weeks in patients with moderate, uncomplicated iron deficiency (about 500–800 mg of iron, enough for 500 to 800 mL of packed red blood cells, or enough to raise the whole blood hemoglobin 2–3 g/dL).^{6, 15}
- Subjects having normal Hb $> 12\text{gm}\%$: Single Tablet containing Ferrous ascorbate/fumerate equivalent to 100 mg of elemental iron + Tab. Folic acid 500mcg + Vit B12 15mcg. Single weekly dose for 1 month. 4 pills were given.^{2, 4}
- Subjects having Mild anaemia (Hb $11 - 11.9\text{gm}\%$): Single Tablet containing Ferrous ascorbate/fumerate equivalent to 100 mg of elemental iron + Tab. Folic acid 500mcg + Vit B12 15mcg. Single Daily dose for 1 month. 30 pills were given.^{11, 14}
- Subjects having moderate anaemia (Hb $8 - 10.9\text{gm}\%$): Single Tablet containing Ferrous ascorbate/fumerate equivalent to 100 mg of elemental iron + Tab. Folic acid 500mcg + Vit B12 15mcg. Twice Daily dose for 1 month. 60 pills were given.^{11, 14}
- Subjects with severe anaemia (Hb $< 8 \text{gm}\%$): were referred to tertiary care and followed up after one month.^{4,6,14}
- ❖ Additional advice: subjects were instructed to take tablets on empty stomach for better absorption. In case of gastritis, nausea, vomiting etc. advice was given to take one hour after meal or at night. If constipation occurs, advise to drink more water and add roughage to diet. IFA tablets should not be consumed with tea, coffee, milk or calcium tablets. Side effects and adverse effects from the drugs were informed in detail to all the subjects.^{6,15}
- ❖ Exclusion of subjects: patients complaining of severe side effects, taking treatment for infertility and $< 21\text{yrs}$ or $> 50\text{yrs}$ age group were referred to tertiary care and excluded from the study.
- ❖ Follow up: after 1 month of dietary modification and active treatment, subjects were asked to come back for follow up. Improvement in signs and symptoms related to dietary deficiency anaemia were reassessed and Hb estimation by Cyanmethemoglobin method was repeated. Improvement in Hb in gm% was noted. Patients were asked to continue treatment for at least 2 more months and maintain diet. If no improvement is seen, patients will be referred to tertiary care for further evaluation.^{1,4}
- ❖ Based on previous studies, structured questioner was used to assess reasons for non-adherence to lifestyle modifications, treatment and follow-up.^{13,16,17}

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

30 subjects were recruited each in category A, B and C. While women in category D (housekeeping/security/gardening) the samples collected were 56. Average age group was in late 30s in category A (Teaching faculty) and D, while category B (staff nurse/Managers/assistant managers/Supervisors) average age was late 20s and category C (senior office assistant/office assistant/lab. Technician/paramedical MSWs) was early 30s. In all the categories, majority of working women had moderate anaemia at the time of diagnosis ($8 - 10.9\text{gm}\%$) but signs and symptoms were < 2 showing lack of

positive correlation. Only in category D, 57.14% of the subjects had ≥ 2 S/S. Dietary modifications were followed on an average for up to 20-25 days by all the categories. Less than 50% women showed up for follow-up Haemoglobin check done after 1 month of initiation of treatment. In subjects who showed up for follow up, average rise in haemoglobin in all the categories was in the range of 0.5 – 1.3gm%. (Table1)

Table 1: Data obtained and analysed				
CATEGORY	A	B	C	D
Total Subjects	30	30	30	56
Average Age (yrs)	37.6 \pm 4.85	28.47 \pm 5.21	32.47 \pm 7.67	38.78 \pm 6.96
PREVALENCE OF ANAEMIA				
NORMAL >12gm%	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	5 (16.67%)	6 (10.71%)
MILD = 11 – 11.9gm%	10 (33.33%)	6 (20%)	10 (33.33%)	9 (16.07%)
MODERATE= 8 – 10.9gm%	16 (53.33%)	19 (63.33%)	14 (46.67%)	38 (67.86%)
SEVERE < 8gm%.	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	1 (3.33%)	3 (5.36%)
SIGNS AND SYMPTOMS OF ANAEMIA				
< 2 S/S	21 (70%)	18 (60%)	18 (60%)	24 (42.86%)
≥ 2 S/S	9 (30%)	12 (40%)	12 (40%)	32 (57.14%)
Follow up of Hb test after one month				
Reported for follow up (repeat Hb)	14 (46.67%)	10 (33.33%)	10 (33.33%)	21 (37.5%)
Average improvement in Hb (in gm%)	0.84	1.31	0.53	1.08

DISCUSSION

146 working women in the age group of 21 -50yrs belonging to different job rankings were included in our study. Irrespective of the cadre in their work place, majority of women showed presence of moderate grade of anaemia based on the assessed Hb(8-10.9gm%). Unlike previous study by Wolmarans P et.al conducted in South Africa, the burden of anaemia among working women in Indian remains high.¹⁴ In women working in higher cadres, this was mainly due to lack of positive correlation in signs and symptoms. Diagnosing anaemia based purely on clinical correlation is not reliable. Previous study by Elnicki DM et al showed only 1 out of 52 patients showed signs of fatigue caused by anaemia.¹⁸ Pallor also was less helpful at diagnosing anaemia with hemoglobin levels as low as 9gm/dl.¹⁹ Other symptoms classical of anemia lie glossitis, koilonychia and dysphagia also remain uncommon.²⁰ Women working in category D had more than 2 signs and symptoms related to degree of anaemia at presentation. In category D the prevalence was mainly due to lack of health insurance / cost of treatment also knowledge of the disease.¹⁴

Dietary modifications were followed on an average by 50% of subjects. The remaining subjects indicated that they were overworked at both home and workplace, along with lack of time management and exhaustion. This was true in all categories of work irrespective of job ranking. Actual and perceived side effects increased with higher dosage in higher grades of anaemia. Percentage of women showing up for follow up Hb estimation was very less (<50% in all categories). This was mainly due to either sense of wellbeing or fear of prick/ blood collection.

CONCLUSION

A prospective interventional study was performed in working women belonging to different job rankings. Prevalence of anaemia among working women in India remains underestimated. Anaemia reduces working capacity and working women do lot of multi-tasking, in the process ignoring their own health. Even with enough knowledge about the disease and its consequences, working women find it challenging to curb the disease. Our study provided free investigation and treatment to patient, yet the subjects could not follow lifestyle modifications, take adequate treatment nor report back for followup. This suggests that the approach to treating anaemia in these subjects should be multi-centric

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